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Impact of Climate-Smart and Water-Saving Frontier Agriculture on the WEFE Nexus in Arid Mediterranean Regions

Practice Abstract

"How to produce mushrooms inside a shipping container in an urban environment"

Responsible Partner

DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE AGRARIE

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Dissemination Level

P	Public	<input type="checkbox"/>
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Introduction

Urban agriculture has long been identified as a valid solution to guarantee food security and the creation of small profitable businesses in developing and non-developing countries. As is known, the number of inhabitants in cities has recently exceeded the number of inhabitants in rural areas, resulting in an extension of the concrete surface and a greater distance from food supply areas. Ensuring a good supply of local, fresh and nutritious food is of fundamental importance in such an environment. Local food production not only contributes to food diversity but also plays a critical role in improving food safety by reducing the risks associated with long-distance supply chains. However, in an urban context, access to arable land is, although not impossible, rather difficult. Over time, urban agriculture has taken on different forms to overcome the problem of the absence of arable land, from the simplest cultivation systems in boxes filled with soil to be placed in unused cemented areas, up to highly technological systems such as those for indoor cultivation in buildings or in shipping container.

Indoor cultivation systems can be particularly versatile for any type of environment, from the hottest to the coldest, allowing you to control all the environmental parameters necessary for the development of a plant, such as light, temperatures and relative humidity. Furthermore, these systems allow you to control and supply the exact quantities of cultivation inputs, such as water and nutrients, thus allowing savings and lower environmental impact. However, given the use of artificial light and cooling, heating, humidification and dehumidification systems, indoor production can require high quantities of energy, with costs that are not always affordable depending on the production area. In addition, the potential environmental impact of waste products, such as nutrient-rich effluents, should not be overlooked.

Problem or challenge addressed

Different types of products can be grown within these indoor systems, however two important aspects must be considered before starting an urban agriculture business with this type of system: the suitability of the species for indoor cultivation and the economic profitability. In fact, protocols for the optimal cultivation of specific species in indoor conditions should be defined to allow achieving the maximum yield. Additionally, the chosen species should exhibit compatibility with the controlled indoor environment, taking into account factors like growth cycles, space requirements, and sensitivity to environmental fluctuations. Furthermore, the high energy and installation costs of these highly technological systems could put the success of the business at risk.

In the next paragraph, the cultivation method, optimal environmental conditions and potential yields for cultivating mushrooms, variety *Pleurotus eryngii*, in a shipping container will be described. Subsequently, hypothetical economic evaluations for the installation of the system in an urban area in Italy will also be reported.

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Solution / Innovation

The shipping container is 12 meters long, large 2.35 and 2.39 meter tall. Inside, there are 2 long shelves with 3/4 growing layers that cover all the two longer sides of the container (Fig. 1). The system is further equipped with a HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) plant. The internal temperature is set on 17°C, a relative humidity of 85% -80% and a photoperiod of 12 h/day, the optimal condition for *Pleurotus eryngii* mushroom.

Fig 1. External view of the container (left) and internal view of the growing layers with bags of *Pleurotus eryngii* (right).

Given the production inside a controlled environment, the cultivation cycle could be started in any moment of the year. The mushroom is cultivated in ready to use bags. The container can host up to 500 bags that will make the first flush of fruiting bodies in 14 days and the second one after other 10 days. Considering a growing cycle of 25 days, it is possible to hypothesize a total of 14 cycles every year in case of a full cultivation regime (Fig. 2). Indeed, using ready to grow bags, it is not necessary to consider the incubation period. However, using this ready to use product is more expensive than producing starting from the inocule, which requests specific facilities that need to be properly designed separated from the production area. The environment of cultivation should always be kept clean and insulated from the outside, in order to avoid external contaminations.

Fig 2. Cultivation cycle of *Pleurotus eryngii*.

Concerning the production costs, the capital expenditure is represented by container purchase and installation, and by the setting and design of electric system. Considering a case study in Italy, a total of 22'000 € of capital expenditure has been considered. The operative expenses are represented by the energy consumption, which are around 67 kWh per week, the purchase of mushrooms bags and the payment of one worker. The purchase of mushrooms bag is the biggest part of the operative expenses, while the energy expenses are quite low. Considering to fully fill the entire container with the bags, it is possible to expect around 0.5-0.6 kg of fruiting bodies for each bag in 14 days, that means a production of 250-300 kg of edible product. The mushrooms could be sell at least at 10 € kg⁻¹, but it is possible to hypothesize a higher price of 15 € kg⁻¹.

The optimal selling price could be estimated as follow. The installation of the container costs 22'000 €. Considering an amortization period of 10 years with an interest rate of 3.575 %, the annual amortization would be around 2'600 €. In case of the operative expenditure, the purchase of the bags has a cost around 30'000 €. The energy consumption is around 3'500 kWh every year, that means a cost of 875 €. Therefore, the estimated selling price would be around 12 € kg⁻¹. An extended evaluation of annual costs and profits is reported in Fig. 3. Taxes and possible fluctuations in demand were not considered in the economic evaluation.

Fig. 3 Evaluation of annual cost and profits for mushrooms production.

Implementation (hands-on, a bit like a cooking recipe)

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Tips and Hints

The emission of fruiting bodies is called flush and the mushrooms *Pleurotus eryngii* could make till 4 flushes with the same bag. However, it is better to only consider the first and second flush, since the fresh weight of product decrease for each flush. Approximatively, it is possible to consider a decreasing of 30% of FW for each flush.

Links to more information (when available)

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PRACTICE ABSTRACT

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